

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin
Volume 2, Nomor 10, November 2024, P. 840-848
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E-Issn: [2986-6340](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14224403)
Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14224403>

Unmasking Women's Oppression In Black Widow (2021): A Deep Dive Into Kevin Feige's Cinematic Narrative

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Abstrak

This research delves into how the film Black Widow (2021) represents the oppression of women and their struggle to resist and free themselves from patriarchal control. By exploring various forms of oppression experienced by the female characters, the study highlights the persistent influence of patriarchal structures, even in the face of determined resistance from the protagonists. Employing qualitative research methods, the study analyzes key scenes and dialogues from the original script to uncover the dynamics of power, control, and resistance. Iris Marion Young's Five Faces of Oppression framework serves as the analytical lens, offering in-depth insights into systemic forms of oppression such as exploitation, violence, and marginalization. Feminist literary criticism is employed as the research approach to examine the experiences of Natasha Romanoff, as the central character, alongside other female characters, in confronting manipulation, bodily exploitation, and the stripping of individual identity imposed by a repressive patriarchal system. The findings reveal that, despite centering on a female superhero, Black Widow reflects the enduring realities of women's subjugation under male dominance and entrenched patriarchal structures. The film also portrays the complexities of resisting such oppression, while emphasizing the potential of resistance as a form of female empowerment. This study asserts Black Widow's significance in addressing gender issues and its contribution to contemporary feminist discourse and popular culture.

Kata kunci: *Oppression, Types, Black Widow Film*

Article Info

Received date: 29 Oktober 2024

Revised date: 19 November 2024

Accepted date: 25 November 2024

INTRODUCTION

The concept of inequality between men and women has evolved over time, encompassing not only political rights but also issues of domination and violence against women. Violence, including physical abuse and systematic control, remains a recurring issue deeply rooted in patriarchal structures (Wollstonecraft, 1792). Feminism, as a theoretical and practical framework, seeks to address these systemic inequalities. Bhasin and Khan (1995) describe feminism as the pursuit of women's emancipation in political, economic, and social spheres, challenging their subordination under male dominance. Similarly, Jati Kusuma (2019) highlights that violence against women often stems from cultural objectification, which desensitizes society to women's suffering.

Oppression, as discussed by Hannam (2007), is not limited to overt acts of violence but extends to stereotypes and societal expectations that confine women to subordinate roles. Stereotypes like being nurturing, gentle, or weak, perpetuate power imbalances and marginalize women's autonomy (Langan, 1998). This cultural narrative relegates women to the domestic sphere and obstructs their potential in public and professional domains. Feminism counters such oppression by advocating for equality, dismantling stereotypes, and challenging systemic injustices.

In media and literature, themes of feminism and oppression have been frequently explored, with films serving as a powerful medium to highlight these issues. One such example is Marvel's *Black Widow* (2021), which portrays a compelling narrative of women's oppression and resistance. Dreykov, the antagonist, exemplifies patriarchal control by kidnapping and brainwashing young girls into assassins under his command. The film's female protagonists resist this oppression, symbolizing the broader feminist struggle against patriarchal structures.

This research examines how *Black Widow* represents the oppression of women and their fight for emancipation. By focusing on the dynamics of power and control depicted in the film, this study

aims to contribute to the broader discourse on feminism and gender equality. Drawing on foundational works such as *The Rights of Woman* (Wollstonecraft, 1792), Hannam (2007), Bhasin and Khan (1995), Jati Kusuma (2019), and Langan (1998), this analysis situates *Black Widow* within the feminist critique of patriarchal systems and highlights its relevance in popular culture as a medium of feminist expression.

METHOD

This research utilized a descriptive qualitative method to analyze how women are oppressed and treated unfairly in the film *Black Widow* (2021). As stated by Bogdan and Taylor (1955), qualitative research produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words and observable behavior. This approach was selected to explore the feminist themes in the film through the lens of feminist literary criticism, specifically using Iris Marion Young's theory of oppression. This framework examines structural and cultural forms of domination that contribute to systemic inequality and marginalization.

The primary data source for this study was the *Black Widow* film, directed by Cate Shortland and produced by Kevin Feige. Secondary data included scholarly articles, books, and critiques on feminist theory, particularly works discussing Iris Marion Young's framework of oppression, which identifies five forms of oppression: violence, marginalization, exploitation, powerlessness, and cultural imperialism. These sources provided theoretical support to analyze the portrayal of women's struggles and oppression in the film.

The data collection process began with repeated viewings of the film to identify key scenes and dialogues that depict various forms of oppression. Notes were taken to document relevant interactions, character arcs, and cinematic elements such as visual symbolism and narrative structure. Secondary sources were reviewed to contextualize the findings and ensure a comprehensive understanding of feminist principles and Young's theoretical perspectives.

Data analysis was conducted thematically by categorizing the findings into the five forms of oppression as outlined by Young. Each category was analyzed in relation to the film's narrative and character development, focusing on how these forms of oppression were depicted and resisted by female characters. The feminist literary criticism approach enabled a critical examination of the power dynamics and societal structures portrayed in *Black Widow*, emphasizing the intersection of gender, power, and resistance. This method ensured a detailed and systematic exploration of the film's feminist themes, allowing for a robust analysis grounded in established theoretical frameworks.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Women Oppression Experience by the Main Character Natasha Romanoff

Oppression reflects the injustice between men and women rooted in patriarchal systems that prioritize male dominance in values, expectations, and decision-making, leaving women oppressed and reliant on men (Ademiluka, 2018). Cudd (2005) defines oppression as unjust conditions, while Young (1990) describes it as practices of domination and violence by ruling groups. Young identifies five forms of oppression: exploitation (using others' power for personal gain), violence (physical or material attacks), cultural imperialism (imposing dominant norms), marginalization (exclusion from opportunities), and powerlessness (domination through authority). This research examines Natasha Romanoff's experiences of violence and oppression, particularly those imposed by Dreykov, analyzing how these conflicts unfold and how Natasha responds to them.

Exploitation

In *Black Widow*, Natasha Romanoff and other women experience physical and psychological exploitation orchestrated by Dreykov and the RedRoom to strip them of autonomy and humanity, turning them into obedient assassins. Physical exploitation is evident in their kidnapping, forced training, and transformation into elite killers from a young age. For instance, Natasha and Yelena were taken from their families and subjected to grueling training that dehumanized them, as seen in the emotional scene in Cuba where young Natasha pleads to protect Yelena, revealing the trauma and loss of freedom imposed by the system.

The RedRoom's exploitation treats the *Black Widows* as tools, with Dreykov justifying his actions by objectifying them as "recycled trash" given purpose. This reveals a patriarchal mindset

where Dreykov positions himself as a savior while devaluing the women as disposable instruments for his ambitions. His control over their physical abilities, combined with his manipulative rhetoric, underscores the inhumane exploitation these women endure, reducing them to weapons molded to serve his goals.

In *Black Widow*, psychological exploitation is a pervasive and insidious tool used by Dreykov and the Red Room to control the *Black Widows*. Through brainwashing, mind control, and chemical enhancements, these women are stripped of their autonomy and personal identity, forced to act against their will. The film captures this devastation, as seen in Ingrid's desperate plea, "I don't wanna do this... He's making me," before being driven to suicide under Dreykov's control. This manipulation, combined with hypnosis and fear, ensures the Widows' unquestioning obedience, leaving them unable to resist or escape. Natasha's internal struggle to reconcile her manipulated past with her true self underscores the psychological toll this exploitation exacts.

Dreykov's view of the *Widows* as mere "natural resources" reveals the depth of this exploitation, reducing them to tools for his schemes of global dominance. His chilling statement, "I can finally come out of the shadows using the only natural resource that the world has too much of: girls," underscores the dehumanization at the heart of his patriarchal system. This exploitation denies the *Widows* any sense of individuality or free will, transforming their lives into instruments of Dreykov's power. The film portrays Natasha's fight to reclaim her autonomy as a powerful narrative of resistance, exposing the profound psychological and emotional damage inflicted by such systems of control.

Violence

This research reveals two forms of violence experienced by Natasha Romanoff in *Black Widow*: physical and psychological violence, both rooted in the control exerted by Dreykov and the RedRoom. Physical violence is evident in the brutal training and coercion inflicted upon Natasha and other *Black Widows*, transforming them into elite assassins through extreme combat conditioning and body control. Kidnapped as children, they were subjected to relentless physical exploitation, such as forced sterilization, which symbolized the suppression of their autonomy and individuality. The violence culminates in their use as weapons, with Dreykov controlling their every move, reducing their bodies to mere tools for his ambitions. Natasha's fear and resistance to returning to the RedRoom as a child further highlight the physical trauma she endured.

RedRoom training is one of the clearest examples of the physical violence experienced by Natasha, the main character in *Black Widow*, from a young age. Alongside other girls her age, Natasha underwent extremely harsh physical training in the Red Room, a program run by a Russian organization. This program aimed to train women to become skilled spies and assassins. In addition to physical and combat training, Natasha was trained in various forms of martial arts, weapon handling, and combat tactics. This training was intensive and dangerous, designed to create highly skilled and lethal operatives.

RedRoom Training (*Black Widow*, 2021)

As in the illustration above, Natasha is taught how to use various types of firearms. Her training includes accuracy in shooting targets to ensure her can shoot accurately from various distances. Quick Reaction, Shooting practice in urgent and stressful situations, improving her reflexes and ability to make quick decisions. Different Weapons Training with a variety of weapons, from pistols to rifles, ensures her is ready for any situation. And if Natasha and the widows cannot pass the training given to them by the RedRoom, then they will face risks such as harsh physical punishment which can include beatings, torture or other forms of physical violence designed to punish and motivate them to be able to do it. successfully passed the exercise. There are also punishments given by the RedRoom itself that result in death, failure to meet RedRoom standards can have fatal consequences for widows, because the RedRoom program does not care about the lives of individuals who it deems useless or not strong enough to become elite agents

Psychological violence, equally pervasive, involves brainwashing, emotional manipulation, and identity erasure. The Red Room's systematic conditioning ensures total obedience by stripping the Black Widows of their free will and implanting false memories. Natasha's guilt over past actions, such as believing she killed Antonia Dreykov, underscores the emotional toll of this manipulation. Additionally, the creation of a fake family dynamic with Alexei, Melina, and Yelena reflects the RedRoom's exploitation of emotional bonds for control. Natasha's dialogue with Yelena about their erased pasts illustrates the depth of their identity crises, as they grapple with fabricated realities and lost childhoods. This psychological violence leaves Natasha with a lasting burden, forcing her to confront her dark past and seek redemption, further emphasizing the devastating impact of the Red Room's oppression.

The RedRoom training program, as depicted in *Black Widow* (2021), is an intense regime that combines physical training, spy skills, brainwashing, and psychological manipulation to ensure absolute loyalty. Participants are subjected to false memories and programmed to obey commands without question, erasing their autonomy. A striking example of this is the brainwashing process shown in a key scene involving Natasha Romanoff.

Brainwashing as Part of Red Room Training (*Black Widow*, 2021)

In this scene, Natasha undergoes a harrowing brainwashing procedure designed to strip away her freedom of thought and resistance. This process highlights the oppressive control imposed on all women in the *Black Widow* program, rendering them mere tools under the Red Room's authority. One of the most severe forms of violence Natasha and other agents endure is forced sterilization, symbolizing the RedRoom's complete domination over their bodies and identities. This act transcends physical harm, embodying psychological oppression by robbing these women of the ability to make choices about their own lives.

During the brainwashing, Natasha displays visible fear and resistance, knowing that once the process begins, she will lose her independence and become fully subservient to Dreykov's control. The scene vividly portrays the loss of autonomy inflicted on *Black Widows*, even someone as resilient as Natasha. The technology used in this process symbolizes patriarchal authority's intent to dominate

women's lives entirely, both physically and mentally. This dual attack on body and mind illustrates the extent of Dreykov's oppressive control, reducing these women to tools of a male-driven agenda.

In *Black Widow* also, Dreykov's patriarchal control forces women like Natasha and Yelena into cycles of violence, even against one another. The RedRoom's conditioning transforms these women into agents who view each other as threats, a dynamic revealed in their first reunion. Despite being adopted sisters, their interaction begins with distrust and escalates into an intense physical fight. This confrontation illustrates how systemic violence strips them of solidarity.

The Impact of RedRoom Violence (*Black Widow*, 2021)

Yelena: (Muffled) "I know you're out there."

Natasha: "I know you know I'm out here."

Yelena: "Then why are you skulking about like it's a minefield?"

Natasha: "'Cause I don't know if I can trust you."

Yelena: (Chuckles) "Funny, I was going to say the same thing."

This dialogue reveals the deep-seated fear and mistrust ingrained by the RedRoom. Years of violence and manipulation make them view each other with suspicion, illustrating how patriarchal control not only exploits women but pits them against one another, perpetuating cycles of conflict and domination.

The control exerted by the RedRoom profoundly impacts not only Natasha and Yelena but also the other Black Widows still under Dreykov's command. One of the clearest consequences is the perpetuation of violence, particularly among women themselves. This dynamic is starkly depicted in the scene where Natasha confronts Dreykov. When Natasha resists, Dreykov activates a threat alarm, compelling the other Widows to attack her. Despite being victims of the same oppressive system, these women, trained as assassins, are forced to inflict violence on one another.

The Impact of Red Room Violence (*Black Widow*, 2021)

This scene illustrates the devastating cycle of violence created by the RedRoom. Under Dreykov's control, women are stripped of autonomy and solidarity, reduced to tools of his power. Instead of uniting to resist their shared oppression, they are manipulated into acting as enforcers of violence against each other. This exploitation not only robs them of their freedom but also fractures potential bonds of sisterhood and mutual support.

The psychological control imposed by the RedRoom destroys their humanity, replacing it with a system of violence and exploitation. This represents one of the most insidious impacts of Dreykov's authority: turning victims into unwilling perpetrators, perpetuating a cycle of harm that undermines their collective strength and individuality.

Cultural Imperialism

In *Black Widow*, cultural imperialism is a key theme, particularly in its focus on controlling women. The RedRoom, under Dreykov's leadership, symbolizes patriarchal domination, systematically stripping women of their identities and autonomy to mold them into tools for patriarchal objectives. This is most strikingly illustrated through forced sterilization, which Yelena describes bluntly:

Yelena: "I don't get my period, dipshit. I don't have a uterus."

Natasha: "Or ovaries."

Yelena: "Yeah. They just go in and rip out all your reproductive organs."

This act is not only physical violence but also a profound psychological blow, robbing these women of reproductive autonomy and reducing their value to their utility as assassins. By enforcing such measures, the RedRoom removes traditional roles tied to motherhood and femininity, positioning women solely as emotionless and submissive weapons under male control.

Furthermore, the RedRoom forces women to conform to a masculine identity dictated by patriarchal ideals, erasing traits like compassion and tenderness, which are deemed weaknesses. By training *Black Widows* to adopt aggressiveness and physical strength—qualities traditionally associated with men—the system suppresses their individuality and humanity. This cultural imperialism perpetuates the view that women are valuable only when they abandon their identity and conform to patriarchal expectations, emphasizing control over both their bodies and identities. Forced sterilization in *Black Widow* exemplifies the RedRoom's absolute control over women's lives, stripping them of their ability to reproduce and form families. This is highlighted in Yelena's poignant question to Natasha:

Yelena: "Did you ever wish you had kids?" (49:34)

This question reflects the deep scars left by the RedRoom's oppressive practices, which reduce women to tools of patriarchal control. The sterilization program embodies multiple facets of oppression as described by Iris Marion Young, including violence, marginalization, powerlessness, cultural imperialism, and exploitation. By erasing the *Black Widows*' natural identities and replacing them with militaristic roles, the Red Room rejects feminist values and imposes a culture that devalues women's autonomy and femininity, reinforcing patriarchal domination at every level.

Marginalization

In *Black Widow*, marginalization is starkly portrayed through the experiences of women who are trapped in the RedRoom program. These women, including Natasha Romanoff, are forcibly recruited and manipulated into becoming lethal assassins under the control of Dreykov. They are stripped of their autonomy and treated as mere tools for violence, with no control over their own bodies or life choices. The most blatant form of marginalization is seen in how Dreykov reduces these women to objects physically and mentally controlled to serve his patriarchal agenda. They are taken from their families, isolated, and conditioned to suppress their own identities and desires. This systemic exploitation denies them basic human rights, such as the freedom to choose their own path in life, form relationships, or experience motherhood.

Natasha, the protagonist, exemplifies the enduring effects of this marginalization. While she escapes the RedRoom, the trauma and control Dreykov imposed on her continue to haunt her. This reflects Iris Marion Young's theory of marginalization, where individuals are excluded from full

participation in society, not only through the denial of their human rights but also by being stripped of their agency and voice. Even after breaking free, Natasha struggles with the psychological scars of a life shaped by an oppressive system that sought to erase her autonomy. The long-term impact of this marginalization is evident, as Natasha and other Black Widows must navigate a world that remains shaped by the trauma inflicted by Dreykov's patriarchal control, reinforcing how deeply such systems can affect individuals, even beyond their immediate experiences of oppression.

Powerlessness

In *Black Widow*, powerlessness is a central theme, especially for Natasha Romanoff and the other *Black Widows*. Despite their physical strength and training as deadly assassins, they are denied the ability to control their lives, bodies, and choices. This lack of autonomy is most clearly seen through the forced sterilization of Natasha and the other women in the RedRoom, where their right to make decisions about their reproductive health is stripped away. These women, while physically formidable, are reduced to tools controlled by Dreykov, the patriarchal figure in charge, who manipulates both their bodies and minds. As Natasha puts it in the film, "You took my childhood, you took my choices, and tried to break me" (*Black Widow*, 1:45:40), highlighting how their lives were dictated by Dreykov's oppressive system.

This powerlessness goes beyond the physical realm, extending into psychological and emotional control. The RedRoom uses both mental manipulation and physical violence to ensure the *Black Widows* remain obedient, with no voice or power to resist. They are trained from childhood to be weapons without personal identity or agency. In her struggle to confront Dreykov, Natasha's statement, "You took my childhood, you took my choices, and tried to break me, but you're never gonna do that to anybody ever again," reflects her recognition of the extent to which her autonomy was stripped away. This moment illustrates the psychological dimensions of powerlessness, where the women are not only controlled externally but also manipulated to lose their sense of self and agency.

Through this, Natasha begins to resist her own powerlessness, a key moment in her character arc. Iris Marion Young's theory of powerlessness is evident in how Dreykov and the RedRoom create a hierarchy where women, particularly Natasha, are subordinated with no opportunity to influence their own lives. Natasha's declaration, "But you're never gonna do that to anybody ever again," signals her resolve to break free from this cycle of oppression and to ensure other women do not suffer the same fate. This marks a shift from submission to resistance, showing Natasha's empowerment as she rejects the patriarchal control that has defined her life. It becomes a moment of reclaiming autonomy and ending the systemic powerlessness imposed by the RedRoom.

In *Black Widow* also, powerlessness is starkly portrayed in the scene where Ingrid, a *Black Widow*, is forced to commit suicide under Dreykov's control.

Powerlessness Over Body Control (*Black Widow*, 2021)

Natasha: Hey. Don't move. You're hurt. Let me help you.

(BREATHING SHAKILY)

(GRUNTS)

(WHIRRING, DEVICE BEEPING)

Ingrid: I don't wanna do this. (SOBBING)

Natasha: What are you doing?
 Ingrid: He's making me.
 (WHIRRING INTENSIFIES)

This scene captures the profound powerlessness experienced by the *Black Widows* under Dreykov's control. Ingrid, gravely injured during a mission, is forced to commit suicide against her will. Her words, "I don't wanna do this" and "He's making me," vividly reflect the helplessness described in Iris Marion Young's theory. The women lack autonomy over their bodies and actions, manipulated by external forces beyond their control.

This moment starkly illustrates how Dreykov's system denies the Widows agency, using them as instruments of his power, even to the point of self-destruction. It emphasizes the depth of their oppression, as they are unable to resist the commands imposed upon them, embodying total disempowerment. This moment exemplifies Iris Marion Young's theory of helplessness, where individuals lose control over their actions and bodies. Ingrid's autonomy is stripped away, as Dreykov uses technology to force her to follow commands. Despite her personal desire to live, she is physically controlled, showcasing how patriarchal power can dominate women's bodies, even through technological means.

This scene highlights the loss of control over crucial decisions, especially life or death, which is central to Young's concept of powerlessness. Ingrid's situation reflects the broader theme of women in patriarchal systems, where their decisions are made by external forces, leaving them with no agency. The technology Dreykov uses symbolizes how patriarchy enforces control, stripping women of autonomy through both physical and technological means. As Young argues, such powerlessness is not just about physical domination but is reinforced by societal and technological structures designed to maintain patriarchal authority. This illustrates how Dreykov's control over Ingrid's body reflects the broader theme of patriarchal systems that keep women in a state of helplessness.

DISCUSSION

In *Black Widow*, the conflict between men and women is portrayed through Dreykov's oppressive control over the *Black Widows*, illustrating Iris Marion Young's Five Faces of Oppression: violence, marginalization, powerlessness, cultural imperialism, and exploitation. Dreykov's Red Room exploits the women as tools for his power, stripping them of autonomy and instilling a sense of helplessness through physical, mental, and emotional control. This structural violence exemplifies Young's concept, where institutions not just individuals perpetrate violence and suppress identity. As the story progresses, Natasha and the other *Black Widows* awaken to the reality of their exploitation, igniting their resistance against Dreykov's control. This marks their rejection of cultural imperialism, as they strive to reclaim their identities and autonomy. Natasha's journey embodies Young's notion that awareness is the first step toward liberation, and her alliance with Yelena reflects Young's emphasis on solidarity in fighting oppression. Together, they attempt to dismantle the Red Room, showcasing the importance of collective support in the pursuit of freedom from patriarchal domination. The alliance between Natasha and Yelena signifies more than personal connection; it's a broader challenge to the patriarchy. Analyzing *Black Widow* through feminist criticism reveals how the film captures themes of identity, solidarity, and the ongoing struggle for autonomy. Natasha's fight becomes not just about action, but about resisting control and redefining herself, portraying a feminist narrative of resilience. In this light, *Black Widow* moves beyond typical action storytelling, offering a rich exploration of gender, power, and resistance.

CONCLUSION

Black Widow (2021) delves into themes of feminism, oppression, gender-based violence, and the struggle for women's liberation through the journey of Natasha Romanoff, played by Scarlett Johansson. The film portrays women's fight to escape patriarchal control while confronting the physical and psychological violence they endure. The Red Room, a secret organization led by Dreykov, symbolizes this patriarchal dominance, exploiting and brainwashing women to serve his interests, stripping them of their identities and autonomy. Forced sterilization emerges as a striking form of violence, denying the Widows their reproductive rights and symbolically rejecting traditional

roles associated with femininity, enforcing cold, emotionless standards. This control over their bodies and minds reflects the systemic subjugation women face under powerful male figures. Despite Natasha and the Widows' efforts to resist, the lasting impact of the violence they've experienced underscores the entrenched nature of such oppressive systems, making full escape challenging. Ultimately, the film delivers a poignant commentary on the enduring fight for women's autonomy and the persistent barriers posed by patriarchal structures.

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